

Sharp Jensen Variance Bounds under Atom-Mass Constraints

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Abstract

We prove sharp variance refinements of Jensen’s inequality for finite atomic random variables whose atoms have mass at least α . For convex functions with nondecreasing curvature, the best lower Jensen–variance constant is obtained from a two-point law with atom masses α and $1 - \alpha$, with the minimal atom at the lower point. The sharp upper constant is analogous, with the minimal atom at the upper point; nonincreasing curvature follows by reflection. The proof uses monotonicity of second divided differences and lower and upper collapse arguments. Applications include Jensen–Nesbitt type inequalities, reciprocal Power–Nesbitt inequalities, mean inequalities, power means, finite-alphabet comparisons between Csiszar f -divergences and Pearson’s χ^2 divergence, and finite-ensemble ambiguity gaps for convex losses.

Running head. Atom-mass Jensen bounds.

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1 Introduction

For a convex function f , Jensen’s inequality says

$$\mathbb{E}f(X) \geq f(\mathbb{E}X).$$

The Jensen gap is

$$J_f(X) = \mathbb{E}f(X) - f(\mathbb{E}X).$$

A classical quantitative problem is to estimate this gap from below in terms of the variance:

$$J_f(X) \geq C \operatorname{Var}(X).$$

For unrestricted distributions, sharp constants in Jensen–variance bounds, such as those of Pittenger and Liao–Berg, are often governed by endpoint or vanishing-mass mechanisms. In this paper we impose a finite atomic constraint: every atom has mass at least $\alpha > 0$.

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This forbids the vanishing-mass extremal mechanism and leads to a different sharp constant.

The lower theorem shows that for convex functions with nondecreasing curvature the sharp lower atom-mass Jensen–variance constant is two-point. The lower point carries the minimal admissible mass α . The upper theorem is the opposite extremal principle: the upper point carries the minimal admissible mass α . The cases of nonincreasing curvature follow by reflection.

We emphasize the distinction from the classical mean–variance bounds of Pittenger. Two-point extremizers in Jensen mean–variance problems are already classical. The contribution here is the atom-mass constrained quotient problem: the variance is used as the normalization and the admissible laws are required to have all atom masses bounded below by α . This point of view also applies to finite-alphabet information inequalities: if likelihood ratios are viewed as an atomic random variable under a reference law with cell masses bounded below, the same constants give sharp comparisons of Csiszar f -divergences with the Pearson χ^2 divergence. A second application is the ambiguity gap in ensemble learning: for a convex loss, the improvement of an averaged predictor over the average individual loss is a Jensen gap, and the present constants give sharp finite-ensemble variance lower bounds for this gap.

2 Notation and divided differences

Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1/2$. Let \mathcal{A}_α be the class of nonconstant finite atomic random variables X with values in $[0, 1)$ such that

$$\mathbb{P}(X = t) \geq \alpha \quad \text{for every } t \in \text{supp}(X).$$

The restriction $\alpha \leq 1/2$ is necessary for nonconstant random variables to exist. If the function has a finite continuous value at 1, endpoint limits at 1 may be included by approximation.

Throughout,

$$\mu = \mathbb{E}X \in (0, 1), \quad J_f(X) = \mathbb{E}f(X) - f(\mu).$$

For x, y, z in the interval, write $f[x, y, z]$ for the second divided difference, with the usual continuous interpretation when points coincide. For distinct x, y, z ,

$$f[x, y, z] = \frac{\frac{f(z)-f(y)}{z-y} - \frac{f(y)-f(x)}{y-x}}{z-x}.$$

If $f \in C^2$, then $f[x, y, z]$ is continuous in the variables and equals $f''(x)/2$ when $x = y = z$.

We also use the Bregman quotient

$$q_\mu(t) = \frac{f(t) - f(\mu) - f'(\mu)(t - \mu)}{(t - \mu)^2}, \quad t \neq \mu,$$

with the continuous value

$$q_\mu(\mu) := \frac{1}{2}f''(\mu).$$

In divided-difference notation,

$$q_\mu(t) = f[t, \mu, \mu]$$

for all t , with the usual repeated-node interpretation at $t = \mu$. Moreover,

$$J_f(X) = \mathbb{E} [q_\mu(X)(X - \mu)^2], \quad \text{Var}(X) = \mathbb{E}(X - \mu)^2.$$

Thus $J_f(X)/\text{Var}(X)$ is a variance-weighted average of values of the Bregman quotient.

Lemma 1 (Monotonicity of second divided differences). *If $f \in C^2$ and f'' is nondecreasing, then $f[x, y, z]$ is nondecreasing in each of its three arguments. If f'' is nonincreasing, then $f[x, y, z]$ is nonincreasing in each argument.*

Proof. By the Hermite–Genocchi formula,

$$f[x, y, z] = \int_{\Delta_2} f''(\lambda_1 x + \lambda_2 y + \lambda_3 z) d\lambda,$$

where $\Delta_2 = \{\lambda_i \geq 0 : \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 1\}$, and $d\lambda$ is the standard two-dimensional Lebesgue measure on this simplex, normalized by $\int_{\Delta_2} 1 d\lambda = 1/2$. Hence $f[x, x, x] = f''(x)/2$. If f'' is nondecreasing, increasing any one of x, y, z increases the integrand pointwise; if f'' is nonincreasing, the inequalities reverse. \square

Remark 1 (Bregman monotonicity and the actual hypothesis). *The Jensen quotient at fixed mean is expressed through the Bregman quotient $q_\mu(t)$. A convenient sufficient condition for monotonicity of q_μ is monotonicity of the curvature f'' , because*

$$q_\mu(t) = \int_0^1 (1-s) f''(\mu + s(t - \mu)) ds.$$

Thus f'' nondecreasing implies q_μ nondecreasing in t , while f'' nonincreasing implies q_μ nonincreasing. For C^3 functions,

$$q_\mu(\mu + h) = \frac{1}{2} f''(\mu) + \frac{1}{6} f'''(\mu) h + O(h^2),$$

so the sign of f''' is the local infinitesimal version of this monotonicity.

However, monotonicity of the single fixed-mean quotient q_μ is not enough for the collapse arguments below. The lower collapse uses quotients centered at the conditional tail mean, such as $q_y(t) = f[t, y, y]$, and also mixed second divided differences such as $f[a, \mu, y]$. The upper collapse similarly uses q_ν for the conditional mean below the maximum. Thus the intrinsic condition behind the proofs is coordinatewise monotonicity of second divided differences:

$$f[x, y, z] \text{ is nondecreasing in each argument.}$$

For C^2 functions this condition is equivalent to monotonicity of f'' . Indeed, coordinatewise monotonicity gives $f[x, x, x] \leq f[y, y, y]$ whenever $x \leq y$, hence $f''(x) \leq f''(y)$. Conversely, nondecreasing f'' and the Hermite–Genocchi formula imply coordinatewise monotonicity. The main theorems are therefore stated using the simpler curvature-monotonicity hypothesis.

3 The main lower theorem

For $0 < u < U_{\alpha, \mu}$, where

$$U_{\alpha, \mu} = \min \left\{ \frac{\mu}{1 - \mu}, \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha} \right\},$$

define

$$a_u = \mu - (1 - \mu)u, \quad b_u = \mu + \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}(1 - \mu)u.$$

Then

$$\alpha a_u + (1 - \alpha)b_u = \mu,$$

and

$$\alpha(a_u - \mu)^2 + (1 - \alpha)(b_u - \mu)^2 = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}(1 - \mu)^2 u^2.$$

Theorem 1 (Sharp lower atom-mass Jensen–variance bound). *Let $f \in C^2([0, 1])$ be convex and assume that f'' is nondecreasing. Let $X \in \mathcal{A}_\alpha$ and let $\mu = \mathbb{E}X$. Then*

$$J_f(X) \geq C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) \operatorname{Var}(X),$$

where the sharp constant is

$$C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha(1 - \mu)^2} \inf_{0 < u < U_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha f(a_u) + (1 - \alpha)f(b_u) - f(\mu)}{u^2}.$$

The constant is best possible. It is attained when the infimum is attained in the open interval, and otherwise is approached by the two-point distributions

$$\mathbb{P}(X = a_u) = \alpha, \quad \mathbb{P}(X = b_u) = 1 - \alpha.$$

4 Tail collapse

Lemma 2 (Tail collapse). *Let $f \in C^2$ be convex with nondecreasing f'' . Let X be finite atomic with leftmost support point a of mass p , and let the conditional distribution of the remaining mass have mean y . Thus*

$$X = \begin{cases} a, & p, \\ Y, & q = 1 - p, \end{cases} \quad \mathbb{E}Y = y,$$

and

$$\mu = pa + qy.$$

Then

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\operatorname{Var}(X)} \geq f[a, \mu, y].$$

Equivalently, replacing the whole right tail Y by its conditional mean y does not increase the Jensen–variance quotient.

Proof. Because X is nonconstant, $0 < p < 1$ and $a < \mu < y$. For the two-point distribution with masses p, q at a, y , one has

$$pf(a) + qf(y) - f(\mu) = f[a, \mu, y](p(a - \mu)^2 + q(y - \mu)^2).$$

This is the standard interpolation identity: the affine part of the quadratic interpolant cancels after taking expectation, and the remaining coefficient is $f[a, \mu, y]$.

Now write

$$J_f(X) = pf(a) + q\mathbb{E}f(Y) - f(\mu).$$

Decompose the tail around its own mean y :

$$\mathbb{E}f(Y) - f(y) = \mathbb{E}[(Y - y)^2 f[Y, y, y]].$$

Since every value of Y is at least a , and $a < \mu < y$, monotonicity of second divided differences gives

$$f[Y, y, y] \geq f[a, y, y] \geq f[a, \mu, y].$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}f(Y) - f(y) \geq f[a, \mu, y] \text{Var}(Y).$$

Adding the collapsed two-point contribution gives

$$J_f(X) \geq f[a, \mu, y] (p(a - \mu)^2 + q(y - \mu)^2 + q \text{Var}(Y)).$$

The expression in parentheses is exactly $\text{Var}(X)$ by the law of total variance. Therefore

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\text{Var}(X)} \geq f[a, \mu, y].$$

□

5 Proof of the main theorem

Let a be the leftmost support point of X , with mass $p \geq \alpha$, and let y be the conditional mean of the remaining mass. By the tail-collapse lemma,

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\text{Var}(X)} \geq f[a, \mu, y].$$

Thus every admissible law is bounded from below by the quotient of the collapsed two-point law with the same left atom, same left-atom mass, and same mean.

For a two-point distribution with lower atom mass p at a and upper point y , the mean condition gives

$$\mu = pa + (1 - p)y, \quad y = \mu + \frac{p}{1 - p}(\mu - a).$$

For fixed $a < \mu$, the upper point y is nondecreasing in p . Since $f[a, \mu, y]$ is nondecreasing in y , the quotient is nondecreasing in p . Therefore the minimum under the constraint $p \geq \alpha$ is obtained at $p = \alpha$. This replacement is feasible: if the original two-point collapse has upper point below 1, then lowering p to α only lowers the upper point.

Putting

$$a = \mu - (1 - \mu)u$$

gives

$$y = \mu + \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}(1 - \mu)u = b_u.$$

The constraints $a \geq 0$ and $b_u < 1$ give $0 < u < U_{\alpha, \mu}$, with endpoint values interpreted as one-sided limits when the endpoint is allowed by a finite continuous extension. For this two-point distribution,

$$\text{Var}(X) = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}(1 - \mu)^2 u^2.$$

Substitution gives the stated formula for $C_{\alpha, +}^f(\mu)$.

For sharpness, choose any sequence u_n for which the displayed infimum is approached and take the corresponding two-point laws $\alpha\delta_{a_{u_n}} + (1 - \alpha)\delta_{b_{u_n}}$. These laws belong to \mathcal{A}_α , have mean μ , and their Jensen–variance quotients are exactly the displayed two-point quotients.

Remark 2 (Equal-weight sharpness). *When $\alpha = 1/n$, the sharp two-point laws in the lower theorem are realized inside the ordinary equal-weight class. Indeed, the two-point law*

$$\frac{1}{n}\delta_a + \frac{n-1}{n}\delta_b$$

is represented by the finite vector (a, b, \dots, b) , up to permutation. Thus all equal-weight finite-sum corollaries below have best possible constants for ordinary sums, not only for the larger atom-mass class.

6 Reflected theorem

If f'' is nonincreasing, define

$$g(t) = f(1 - t), \quad Y = 1 - X.$$

Then g'' is nondecreasing. Applying the lower theorem to g and Y gives the reflected bound.

Let

$$V_{\alpha,\mu} = \min \left\{ \frac{1-\mu}{\mu}, \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \right\},$$

and for $0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}$ define

$$c_u = \mu(1 + u), \quad d_u = \mu \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}u \right).$$

Then

$$\alpha c_u + (1 - \alpha)d_u = \mu,$$

and

$$\alpha(c_u - \mu)^2 + (1 - \alpha)(d_u - \mu)^2 = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\mu^2 u^2.$$

Let \mathcal{A}_α^- denote the class of nonconstant finite atomic random variables supported in $(0, 1]$ such that

$$\mathbb{P}(X = t) \geq \alpha \quad (t \in \text{supp } X).$$

Corollary 1 (Sharp lower bound for nonincreasing curvature). *Let f be convex on $(0, 1]$, assume $f \in C^2((0, 1])$, and assume that f'' is nonincreasing. If $X \in \mathcal{A}_\alpha^-$, then*

$$J_f(X) \geq C_{\alpha,-}^f(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

where

$$C_{\alpha,-}^f(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha\mu^2} \inf_{0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha f(c_u) + (1-\alpha)f(d_u) - f(\mu)}{u^2}.$$

If f has a finite continuous extension to 0, endpoint values at 0 may also be included by approximation. The extremal atom of mass α is placed at the upper point.

7 The sharp upper theorem

We now prove the corresponding sharp upper bound. The value of the upper constant may be $+\infty$ for barrier functions.

For $0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}$, where

$$V_{\alpha,\mu} = \min \left\{ \frac{1-\mu}{\mu}, \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \right\},$$

define

$$c_u = \mu(1+u), \quad d_u = \mu \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}u \right).$$

Then

$$\alpha c_u + (1-\alpha)d_u = \mu,$$

and

$$\alpha(c_u - \mu)^2 + (1-\alpha)(d_u - \mu)^2 = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\mu^2 u^2.$$

Lemma 3 (Upper Bregman baseline). *Let $f \in C^2$ be convex with nondecreasing f'' . Let Y be a finite atomic random variable with mean ν and support bounded above by b . Then*

$$J_f(Y) \leq q_\nu(b) \text{Var}(Y).$$

Proof. Since f'' is nondecreasing, $q_\nu(t) = f[t, \nu, \nu]$ is nondecreasing in t . Therefore $q_\nu(Y) \leq q_\nu(b)$ pointwise. Using

$$J_f(Y) = \mathbb{E} [q_\nu(Y)(Y - \nu)^2]$$

gives the claim. □

Lemma 4 (Upper collapse below the maximum). *Let $f \in C^2$ be convex with nondecreasing f'' . Let X be finite atomic with rightmost support point b of mass P , and let the conditional distribution of the remaining mass have mean ν . Thus*

$$X = \begin{cases} b, & P, \\ Y, & Q = 1 - P, \end{cases} \quad \mathbb{E}Y = \nu,$$

and

$$\mu = Pb + Q\nu.$$

Then

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\text{Var}(X)} \leq \frac{Pf(b) + Qf(\nu) - f(\mu)}{P(b - \mu)^2 + Q(\nu - \mu)^2}.$$

Equivalently, replacing all mass below the maximum by its conditional mean does not decrease the Jensen–variance quotient.

Proof. Because X is nonconstant, $0 < P < 1$ and $\nu < \mu < b$. Put

$$B = \frac{Pf(b) + Qf(\nu) - f(\mu)}{P(b - \mu)^2 + Q(\nu - \mu)^2}.$$

The decompositions

$$J_f(X) = QJ_f(Y) + Pf(b) + Qf(\nu) - f(\mu)$$

and

$$\text{Var}(X) = Q \text{Var}(Y) + P(b - \mu)^2 + Q(\nu - \mu)^2$$

show that it is enough to prove

$$J_f(Y) \leq B \text{Var}(Y).$$

By the upper Bregman baseline, it is enough to prove $q_\nu(b) \leq B$.

Let $r = b - \nu$ and set

$$\phi(s) = f(\nu + rs), \quad 0 \leq s \leq 1.$$

Subtracting an affine function from ϕ does not change Jensen gaps or second divided differences, so assume

$$\phi(0) = 0, \quad \phi'(0) = 0.$$

The point μ corresponds to $s = P$. Hence

$$q_\nu(b) = \frac{\phi(1)}{r^2}, \quad B = \frac{P\phi(1) - \phi(P)}{P(1-P)r^2}.$$

Thus $q_\nu(b) \leq B$ is equivalent to

$$\phi(P) \leq P^2\phi(1).$$

For $s > 0$,

$$\frac{\phi(s)}{s^2} = \int_0^1 (1 - \theta)\phi''(\theta s) d\theta.$$

Since ϕ'' is nondecreasing, $\phi(s)/s^2$ is nondecreasing in s . Therefore

$$\frac{\phi(P)}{P^2} \leq \phi(1),$$

which proves the desired inequality. \square

Lemma 5 (Upper atom-mass monotonicity). *Let $f \in C^2$ be convex with nondecreasing f'' . Fix μ and $d > 0$, and consider two-point laws with upper point $b = \mu + d$ of mass P and lower point*

$$a(P) = \mu - \frac{P}{1-P}d$$

of mass $1 - P$. Their Jensen-variance quotient is nonincreasing in P on the range where $a(P)$ belongs to the interval.

Proof. Let $q(t) = q_\mu(t)$ and $q_b = q(b)$. For the two-point law,

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\text{Var}(X)} = Pq(a(P)) + (1-P)q_b = q_b - P(q_b - q(a(P))).$$

Since f'' is nondecreasing, q is nondecreasing. As P increases, $a(P)$ decreases, so $q(a(P))$ is nonincreasing and $q_b - q(a(P))$ is nondecreasing. This quantity is also nonnegative because $a(P) < b$. Hence

$$P(q_b - q(a(P)))$$

is nondecreasing in P , and the quotient is nonincreasing. \square

Theorem 2 (Sharp upper atom-mass Jensen–variance bound). *Let $f \in C^2([0, 1])$ be convex and assume that f'' is nondecreasing. Let $X \in \mathcal{A}_\alpha$ and let $\mu = \mathbb{E}X$. Then*

$$J_f(X) \leq D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) \operatorname{Var}(X),$$

where the sharp extended constant is

$$D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha\mu^2} \sup_{0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha f(c_u) + (1-\alpha)f(d_u) - f(\mu)}{u^2}.$$

The constant is best possible. It is attained when the supremum is attained in the open interval, and otherwise is approached by the two-point distributions

$$\mathbb{P}(X = c_u) = \alpha, \quad \mathbb{P}(X = d_u) = 1 - \alpha.$$

Proof. Let b be the rightmost support point of X , with mass $P \geq \alpha$, and let ν be the conditional mean of the remaining mass. By the upper collapse lemma,

$$\frac{J_f(X)}{\operatorname{Var}(X)} \leq \frac{Pf(b) + (1-P)f(\nu) - f(\mu)}{P(b-\mu)^2 + (1-P)(\nu-\mu)^2}.$$

Thus the supremum is reduced to a two-point problem with upper atom mass $P \geq \alpha$. For fixed upper point $b = \mu + d$, the upper atom-mass monotonicity lemma shows that the quotient is nonincreasing in P . Therefore the maximum under $P \geq \alpha$ is obtained at $P = \alpha$. This replacement is feasible: lowering P to α moves the lower point upward, so it remains in the interval whenever the original lower point was admissible.

Putting $b = \mu + \mu u = \mu(1 + u) = c_u$ gives

$$a = \mu - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\mu u = d_u.$$

The constraints $b < 1$ and $a \geq 0$ give $0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}$. For this two-point law,

$$\operatorname{Var}(X) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\mu^2 u^2.$$

Substitution gives the stated formula. Sharpness follows from the same two-point family. \square

Proposition 1 (Infinite upper constants at a barrier endpoint). *Assume $f(t) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $t \uparrow 1$ and f'' is nondecreasing. If $\mu \geq \alpha$, then*

$$D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = +\infty.$$

Proof. For $\varepsilon > 0$, take

$$\mathbb{P}(X_\varepsilon = 1 - \varepsilon) = \alpha, \quad \mathbb{P}(X_\varepsilon = d_\varepsilon) = 1 - \alpha,$$

where

$$d_\varepsilon = \frac{\mu - \alpha(1 - \varepsilon)}{1 - \alpha}.$$

Then $\mathbb{E}X_\varepsilon = \mu$. If $\mu \geq \alpha$, then $d_\varepsilon \geq 0$ for all sufficiently small ε . Moreover the variance stays bounded and bounded away from zero as $\varepsilon \downarrow 0$, unless $\mu = 1$, which is outside the nonconstant setting on $[0, 1)$. Since $f(1 - \varepsilon) \rightarrow +\infty$, the quotient $J_f(X_\varepsilon)/\operatorname{Var}(X_\varepsilon)$ tends to $+\infty$. \square

Corollary 2 (Sharp upper bound for nonincreasing curvature). *Let f be convex on $(0, 1]$, assume $f \in C^2((0, 1])$, and assume that f'' is nonincreasing. If X is supported in $(0, 1]$ and belongs to the corresponding atom-mass class, then*

$$J_f(X) \leq D_{\alpha,-}^f(\mu) \operatorname{Var}(X),$$

where

$$D_{\alpha,-}^f(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha(1-\mu)^2} \sup_{0 < u < U_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha f(a_u) + (1-\alpha)f(b_u) - f(\mu)}{u^2}.$$

The extremal atom of mass α is placed at the lower point. The statement follows by applying the upper theorem to $g(t) = f(1-t)$ and $Y = 1-X$.

8 Affine transfer to an arbitrary interval

The normalization to $[0, 1)$ is only for notation. Let $I = [A, B)$ with $A < B$, and let $\mathcal{A}_\alpha(I)$ be the class of nonconstant finite atomic random variables supported in I whose atom masses are at least α . For $X \in \mathcal{A}_\alpha(I)$ put

$$m = \mathbb{E}X, \quad \mu = \frac{m-A}{B-A}, \quad Z = \frac{X-A}{B-A}.$$

Then $Z \in \mathcal{A}_\alpha$, $\mathbb{E}Z = \mu$, and

$$\operatorname{Var}(X) = (B-A)^2 \operatorname{Var}(Z).$$

For a function f on I , define

$$F(t) = f(A + (B-A)t), \quad 0 \leq t < 1.$$

Then

$$J_f(X) = J_F(Z), \quad F''(t) = (B-A)^2 f''(A + (B-A)t).$$

Thus monotonicity of f'' on I is equivalent to monotonicity of F'' on $[0, 1)$, and the normalized theorems apply directly.

For example, if f'' is nondecreasing on $[A, B)$, then

$$C_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) = \frac{1}{(B-A)^2} C_{\alpha,+}^F(\mu), \quad D_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) = \frac{1}{(B-A)^2} D_{\alpha,+}^F(\mu),$$

and

$$C_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) \operatorname{Var}(X) \leq J_f(X) \leq D_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) \operatorname{Var}(X).$$

Equivalently, writing

$$a_u = m - (B-m)u, \quad b_u = m + \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(B-m)u,$$

and

$$c_u = m + (m-A)u, \quad d_u = m - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(m-A)u,$$

one has

$$U_{\alpha,m}^I = \min \left\{ \frac{m-A}{B-m}, \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \right\}, \quad V_{\alpha,m}^I = \min \left\{ \frac{B-m}{m-A}, \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \right\},$$

and the constants can be written directly as

$$C_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha(B-m)^2} \inf_{0 < u < U_{\alpha,m}^I} \frac{\alpha f(a_u) + (1-\alpha)f(b_u) - f(m)}{u^2},$$

$$D_{\alpha,+}^{f,I}(m) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha(m-A)^2} \sup_{0 < u < V_{\alpha,m}^I} \frac{\alpha f(c_u) + (1-\alpha)f(d_u) - f(m)}{u^2}.$$

The nonincreasing-curvature constants on $(A, B]$ follow by the same reflection or, equivalently, by applying the displayed transfer to $x \mapsto f(A+B-x)$. Endpoint values at A or B are interpreted in the same one-sided limiting sense as in the normalized interval.

9 Applications

The following examples first spell out lower constants. The upper theorem gives the corresponding reverse estimates whenever the sharp upper constant is finite; for barrier functions it also identifies when no finite upper variance bound can hold.

9.1 The reciprocal Jensen–Nesbitt function

Let

$$f(t) = \frac{t}{1-t}.$$

Then $f''(t) = 2(1-t)^{-3}$ is nondecreasing. The lower theorem gives

$$\mathbb{E} \frac{X}{1-X} - \frac{\mu}{1-\mu} \geq C_{\alpha}^{\text{rec}}(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

where

$$C_{\alpha}^{\text{rec}}(\mu) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-\alpha}{(1-\mu)(1-\mu-\alpha)}, & \alpha \leq \frac{1-\mu}{2}, \\ \frac{4\alpha(1-\alpha)}{(1-\mu)^3}, & \alpha \geq \frac{1-\mu}{2}. \end{cases}$$

At the boundary $\alpha = (1-\mu)/2$ the two expressions agree.

Indeed, for the two-point family in the lower theorem, put $A = 1-\mu$ and $\beta = \alpha/(1-\alpha)$. Then

$$1-a_u = A(1+u), \quad 1-b_u = A(1-\beta u),$$

and the two-point Jensen gap is

$$\frac{1}{A} \left(\frac{\alpha}{1+u} + \frac{1-\alpha}{1-\beta u} - 1 \right) = \frac{\beta u^2}{A(1+u)(1-\beta u)}.$$

Therefore the reciprocal constant is the reciprocal of $A^3(1+u)(1-\beta u)$, minimized by maximizing the concave quadratic $(1+u)(1-\beta u)$ on the admissible interval. This gives the displayed piecewise formula.

For equal weights $\alpha = 1/n$ and mean $\mu = 1/n$, with $n \geq 3$, this gives

$$C_{\alpha}^{\text{rec}}(\mu) = \frac{n}{n-2}.$$

Thus, if $x_1, \dots, x_n > 0$ and $\sum_i x_i = 1$, then

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{1-x_i} - \frac{n}{n-1} \geq \frac{n}{n-2} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(x_i - \frac{1}{n}\right)^2.$$

For $n = 3$, writing $x_1 = a/(a+b+c)$, $x_2 = b/(a+b+c)$, and $x_3 = c/(a+b+c)$, this becomes the sharpened Nesbitt inequality

$$\frac{a}{b+c} + \frac{b}{c+a} + \frac{c}{a+b} \geq \frac{3}{2} + \frac{(a-b)^2 + (b-c)^2 + (c-a)^2}{(a+b+c)^2}.$$

9.2 Dual reciprocal Power–Nesbitt functions

Let

$$F_p(t) = \frac{1-t}{t^p} = t^{-p} - t^{1-p}, \quad p > 0, \quad 0 < t < 1.$$

Then

$$F_p''(t) = p((p+1) - (p-1)t)t^{-p-2} > 0$$

and

$$F_p'''(t) = p(p+1)((p-1)t - (p+2))t^{-p-3} < 0.$$

Thus F_p is convex and has nonincreasing curvature. The reflected theorem applies.

For equal weights, let $t_i > 0$ and $\sum_i t_i = 1$. Then

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1-t_i}{t_i^p} \geq (n-1)n^p + C_{n,p}^\vee \sum_{i=1}^n \left(t_i - \frac{1}{n}\right)^2},$$

where the sharp constant is

$$\boxed{C_{n,p}^\vee = \inf_{r>1} n(r+n-1)^2 \frac{(r+n-1)^{p-1}(r+n-2+r^{-p}) - n^p}{(r-1)^2}}.$$

Indeed, the extremal two-point law has one atom of mass $1/n$ at the upper point and mass $(n-1)/n$ at the lower point. Equivalently, the extremal vector has the form

$$\left(\frac{1}{r+n-1}, \dots, \frac{1}{r+n-1}, \frac{r}{r+n-1}\right), \quad r > 1.$$

The denominator is

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(t_i - \frac{1}{n}\right)^2 = \frac{(n-1)(r-1)^2}{n(r+n-1)^2},$$

and direct substitution gives the displayed quotient. Sharpness follows from the sharpness part of the reflected atom-mass theorem.

In the original homogeneous variables $x_i > 0$, $S = \sum_i x_i$, and $t_i = x_i/S$, this becomes

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{S-x_i}{x_i^p} \geq (n-1)n^p S^{1-p} + C_{n,p}^\vee S^{-p-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(x_i - \frac{S}{n}\right)^2}.$$

The power of S is S^{1-p} , since

$$\frac{S - x_i}{x_i^p} = S^{1-p} \frac{1 - t_i}{t_i^p}.$$

For $p = 1$ the constant is explicit:

$$\boxed{C_{n,1}^\vee = 4n(n-1)}.$$

Indeed,

$$(r+n-1)^0(r+n-2+r^{-1}) - n = r-2+r^{-1} = \frac{(r-1)^2}{r},$$

so

$$C_{n,1}^\vee = \inf_{r>1} n \frac{(r+n-1)^2}{r} = 4n(n-1),$$

with the minimum at $r = n - 1$.

Consequently,

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t_i} \geq n^2 + 4n(n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left(t_i - \frac{1}{n}\right)^2}.$$

The nontrivial equality cases are the permutations of

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2(n-1)}, \dots, \frac{1}{2(n-1)}\right).$$

The ordinary curvature bound on $(0, 1)$ gives only

$$\frac{1}{2} \inf_{0<t<1} F_p''(t) = p.$$

Thus the equal-atom constant is strictly sharper; for $p = 1$ the improvement factor is $4n(n-1)$.

9.3 Harmonic and logarithmic mean corollaries

The previous endpoint $p = 1$ gives a sharp harmonic-mean stability estimate. Let $x_i > 0$ and

$$A = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i, \quad H = \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n 1/x_i}.$$

Applying the reciprocal simplex inequality to $t_i = x_i/(nA)$ gives

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i} \geq \frac{n}{A} + \frac{4(n-1)}{n^2 A^3} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - A)^2}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\boxed{H \leq \frac{A}{1 + \frac{4(n-1)}{n^3 A^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - A)^2}}.$$

The coefficient is sharp, because it is the $p = 1$ endpoint of the sharp dual reciprocal Power–Nesbitt estimate.

For the logarithmic Jensen function

$$L(t) = -\log t, \quad 0 < t < 1,$$

the curvature $L''(t) = t^{-2}$ is nonincreasing. Hence, for $t_i > 0$ and $\sum_i t_i = 1$,

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n -\log t_i \geq n \log n + C_n^{\log} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(t_i - \frac{1}{n}\right)^2},$$

where

$$\boxed{C_n^{\log} = \inf_{r>1} \frac{n(r+n-1)^2}{(n-1)(r-1)^2} \left[n \log \frac{r+n-1}{n} - \log r \right]}.$$

Sharpness again follows from the reflected atom-mass theorem and the one-parameter two-point family displayed in the constant. Therefore, if

$$G = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{1/n},$$

then

$$\boxed{G \leq A \exp \left(-\frac{C_n^{\log}}{n^3 A^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - A)^2 \right)}.$$

These two estimates are included as classical mean corollaries of the atom-mass Jensen theorem, rather than as separate refinements of the extensive AM–GM–HM literature.

9.4 Power sums at fixed arithmetic mean

The monomial examples below can also be written in the usual fixed-mean form. Let $x_i > 0$, let

$$A = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i,$$

and let $p > 1$. Then

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p \geq nA^p + K_{n,p} A^{p-2} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - A)^2}.$$

Here $K_{n,p}$ is the equal-weight sharp constant obtained from the two-point law in the normalized simplex $t_i = x_i/(nA)$. The constants below are sharp by the corresponding lower or reflected atom-mass theorem.

For $1 < p < 2$,

$$\boxed{K_{n,p} = \inf_{r>1} \frac{(n-1+r)^2}{(n-1)(r-1)^2} \left[n^{p-1} \frac{n-1+r^p}{(n-1+r)^p} - 1 \right]}.$$

For $p = 2$,

$$\boxed{K_{n,2} = 1},$$

which is the identity

$$\sum_i x_i^2 - nA^2 = \sum_i (x_i - A)^2.$$

For $p > 2$,

$$K_{n,p} = \inf_{r>1} \frac{(1 + (n-1)r)^2}{(n-1)(r-1)^2} \left[n^{p-1} \frac{1 + (n-1)r^p}{(1 + (n-1)r)^p} - 1 \right].$$

The case $p > 2$ illustrates the finite-atom effect especially clearly: without a lower bound on the variables, the ordinary curvature bound gives zero, whereas the equal-weight fixed-mean geometry gives the positive constant $K_{n,p}$.

9.5 The logarithmic barrier

For

$$f(t) = -\log(1-t),$$

the lower theorem gives

$$\mathbb{E}[-\log(1-X)] + \log(1-\mu) \geq C_\alpha^{\log}(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

where

$$C_\alpha^{\log}(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha(1-\mu)^2} \inf_{0 < u < U_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{-\alpha \log(1+u) - (1-\alpha) \log\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}u\right)}{u^2}.$$

9.6 Monomials

For $f(t) = t^k$, $k \geq 2$,

$$\mathbb{E}X^k - \mu^k \geq C_\alpha^{(k)}(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

where

$$C_\alpha^{(k)}(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha(1-\mu)^2} \inf_{0 < u < U_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha a_u^k + (1-\alpha)b_u^k - \mu^k}{u^2}.$$

For $k = 2$, $C_\alpha^{(2)}(\mu) = 1$. For $k = 3$,

$$C_\alpha^{(3)}(\mu) = \begin{cases} \mu \frac{2-\alpha}{1-\alpha}, & \alpha \leq 1-\mu, \\ 2 + \mu - \frac{1-\mu}{\alpha}, & \alpha \geq 1-\mu. \end{cases}$$

The cubic formula follows from the identity

$$\mathbb{E}X^3 - \mu^3 = 3\mu \text{Var}(X) + \mathbb{E}(X - \mu)^3.$$

For the two-point family this gives the quotient

$$3\mu + (1-\mu)u \frac{2\alpha-1}{1-\alpha}.$$

Since $\alpha \leq 1/2$, this is nonincreasing in u , so the infimum is attained at the largest admissible value of u , namely $\min\{\mu/(1-\mu), (1-\alpha)/\alpha\}$. The two possible active endpoints are exactly the two cases displayed above.

9.7 Fractional powers

For $1 < p < 2$, the function $f(t) = t^p$ has nonincreasing curvature on $(0, 1]$. The reflected lower theorem gives

$$\mathbb{E}X^p - \mu^p \geq C_{\alpha,-}^{(p)}(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

where

$$C_{\alpha,-}^{(p)}(\mu) = \mu^{p-2} \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \inf_{0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha(1+u)^p + (1-\alpha)\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}u\right)^p - 1}{u^2}.$$

This includes endpoint 0 only by the finite continuous extension of t^p at 0.

9.8 Upper-side consequences

For the reciprocal, logarithmic barrier, and more generally for functions with

$$f(t) \rightarrow +\infty \quad (t \uparrow 1),$$

the sharp upper constant in the nondecreasing-curvature case is infinite when $\mu \geq \alpha$. This includes the equal-weight Jensen–Nesbitt normalization $\mu = \alpha = 1/n$: the lower refinement is finite and sharp, but there is no finite upper variance refinement on the same atom-mass class.

If $\mu < \alpha$, then every admissible atom satisfies

$$x_i \leq \frac{\mu}{\alpha} < 1,$$

so the singular endpoint is inaccessible. In that regime the upper theorem gives the finite sharp constant

$$D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha\mu^2} \sup_{0 < u < V_{\alpha,\mu}} \frac{\alpha f(c_u) + (1-\alpha)f(d_u) - f(\mu)}{u^2},$$

with $V_{\alpha,\mu} = (1-\alpha)/\alpha$.

9.9 Further examples

The lower and upper theorems apply to functions with monotone curvature, including

$$e^{\lambda t} \quad (\lambda > 0), \quad (1-t)^{-q} \quad (q > 0), \quad \frac{t}{(1-t)^q} \quad (q > 0),$$

and to polynomials

$$f(t) = a_0 + a_1 t + \sum_{k \geq 2} a_k t^k, \quad a_k \geq 0.$$

Affine terms do not affect the Jensen gap.

10 Finite-alphabet divergence comparisons

The atom-mass formulation has a natural information-theoretic consequence. Let $P = (p_i)$ and $Q = (q_i)$ be probability vectors on a finite alphabet, and assume that

$$q_i \geq \eta > 0 \quad \text{for every } i.$$

Put

$$R_i = \frac{p_i}{q_i}.$$

Then, under the probability law Q , the random variable R satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}_Q R = \sum_i q_i \frac{p_i}{q_i} = 1$$

and all atoms have mass at least η . Moreover,

$$\text{Var}_Q(R) = \sum_i q_i \left(\frac{p_i}{q_i} - 1 \right)^2 = \chi^2(P\|Q),$$

the Pearson chi-square divergence. If f is convex and normalized by $f(1) = 0$, the Csiszar f -divergence is exactly the Jensen gap

$$D_f(P\|Q) = \sum_i q_i f\left(\frac{p_i}{q_i}\right) = \mathbb{E}_Q f(R) - f(\mathbb{E}_Q R).$$

Since $q_i \geq \eta$, one also has

$$0 \leq R_i \leq \frac{1}{\eta}.$$

Thus the interval version of the main theorem applies on $[0, 1/\eta]$ with mean 1.

Corollary 3 (Sharp atom-mass comparison with Pearson divergence). *Let $0 < \eta \leq 1/2$, let P, Q be finite probability vectors with $q_i \geq \eta$, and let $M = 1/\eta$. Let f be convex on $[0, M]$, normalized by $f(1) = 0$, with monotone curvature on $(0, M)$. Then*

$$D_f(P\|Q) \geq \mathcal{C}_\eta^f \chi^2(P\|Q),$$

where

$$\mathcal{C}_\eta^f = \begin{cases} C_{\eta,+}^{f,[0,M]}(1), & f'' \text{ is nondecreasing,} \\ C_{\eta,-}^{f,[0,M]}(1), & f'' \text{ is nonincreasing,} \end{cases}$$

with the constants understood in the interval-normalized sense of the preceding section and, in the second line, through reflection. The constant is best possible in the class $q_i \geq \eta$.

Proof. Apply the corresponding Jensen–variance theorem to the random variable $R = p_i/q_i$ under the probability law Q . The atom masses are the q_i , hence are bounded below by η . The Jensen gap is $D_f(P\|Q)$ and the variance is $\chi^2(P\|Q)$. Sharpness follows already on a two-point alphabet $Q = (\eta, 1 - \eta)$ by taking the extremal two-point likelihood ratio from the main theorem. \square

This corollary should be compared with Green-function and curvature-norm approaches to Jensen gaps and f -divergences. Here the constant relative to $\chi^2(P\|Q)$ is sharp under the structural condition $q_i \geq \eta$, rather than coming from a pointwise Bregman-quotient infimum.

Example 1 (Kullback–Leibler divergence). *For*

$$f(t) = t \log t,$$

one has $f''(t) = 1/t$, so the curvature is nonincreasing. Therefore

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P\|Q) \geq \mathcal{C}_\eta^{\text{KL}} \chi^2(P\|Q),$$

where the sharp constant is the one-dimensional quantity

$$\mathcal{C}_\eta^{\text{KL}} = \inf_{r>1} \frac{A_r^2}{\eta(1-\eta)(r-1)^2} \left[\frac{\eta r}{A_r} \log r - \log A_r \right], \quad A_r = 1 - \eta + \eta r.$$

Indeed, the reflected two-point extremizer has likelihood-ratio values

$$a_r = \frac{1}{A_r}, \quad b_r = \frac{r}{A_r},$$

with Q -masses $1 - \eta$ and η , respectively. Since

$$(1 - \eta)a_r + \eta b_r = 1,$$

the Jensen gap equals

$$(1 - \eta)a_r \log a_r + \eta b_r \log b_r = \frac{\eta r}{A_r} \log r - \log A_r,$$

and the variance equals

$$\eta(1 - \eta) \frac{(r - 1)^2}{A_r^2}.$$

The displayed quotient follows. The constant is sharp on two-point alphabets.

Example 2 (Reverse Kullback–Leibler divergence). For

$$f(t) = -\log t,$$

one obtains $D_f(P\|Q) = D_{\text{KL}}(Q\|P)$ when P has full support. The curvature $f''(t) = t^{-2}$ is nonincreasing, and hence

$$D_{\text{KL}}(Q\|P) \geq \mathcal{C}_\eta^{\text{rKL}} \chi^2(P\|Q),$$

with sharp constant

$$\mathcal{C}_\eta^{\text{rKL}} = \inf_{r>1} \frac{A_r^2}{\eta(1-\eta)(r-1)^2} [\log A_r - \eta \log r], \quad A_r = 1 - \eta + \eta r.$$

If some $p_i = 0$, the reverse Kullback–Leibler divergence is infinite and the inequality is understood in the usual extended sense.

Example 3 (Power divergences). For $\gamma > 1$, $\gamma \neq 1$, consider the Cressie–Read power-divergence generator

$$f_\gamma(t) = \frac{t^\gamma - \gamma t + \gamma - 1}{\gamma(\gamma - 1)}.$$

Then $f_\gamma(1) = 0$ and

$$f_\gamma''(t) = t^{\gamma-2}.$$

Thus the curvature is nonincreasing for $1 < \gamma < 2$, constant for $\gamma = 2$, and nondecreasing for $\gamma > 2$. Consequently

$$D_{f_\gamma}(P\|Q) \geq \mathcal{C}_{n,\gamma} \chi^2(P\|Q)$$

with sharp atom-mass constant obtained from the appropriate one-dimensional two-point formula. In particular, for $\gamma = 2$,

$$f_2(t) = \frac{(t-1)^2}{2}, \quad D_{f_2}(P\|Q) = \frac{1}{2} \chi^2(P\|Q),$$

so the sharp constant is exactly

$$\mathcal{C}_{n,2} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

This is the quadratic degenerate case: the Jensen gap is already an exact multiple of the variance.

11 Ensemble ambiguity gaps for convex losses

A second application is to ensemble averaging. Let z_1, \dots, z_n be scalar predictions or scores and let

$$\bar{z} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n z_i.$$

For a convex loss profile f , Jensen's inequality gives

$$f(\bar{z}) \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(z_i).$$

Thus the ensemble improvement over the average individual loss is the Jensen ambiguity gap

$$\mathcal{G}_f(z_1, \dots, z_n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(z_i) - f(\bar{z}).$$

The classical ambiguity decomposition for squared loss is exactly the special case in which this gap is the empirical variance of the predictions. For general convex losses, ambiguity decompositions in machine learning are often second-order or approximate. The atom-mass Jensen theorem gives a sharp finite-ensemble lower bound whenever the loss profile has monotone curvature.

Corollary 4 (Sharp finite-ensemble ambiguity bound). *Let f be convex on an interval containing z_1, \dots, z_n and assume that f'' is monotone on that interval. Put $\bar{z} = n^{-1} \sum_i z_i$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(z_i) - f(\bar{z}) \geq \mathfrak{C}_{n,f}(\bar{z}) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (z_i - \bar{z})^2,$$

where $\mathfrak{C}_{n,f}(\bar{z})$ is the corresponding sharp atom-mass constant with $\alpha = 1/n$, after the affine normalization of the interval. The constant is best possible for equal-weight ensembles.

Proof. Apply the lower atom-mass theorem to the discrete random variable that takes values z_i with probabilities $1/n$. The Jensen gap is \mathcal{G}_f and the variance is $n^{-1} \sum_i (z_i - \bar{z})^2$. Sharpness is realized by one-vs-all equal-weight vectors of the form (a, b, \dots, b) , after undoing the affine normalization. \square

Example 4 (Squared loss and classical ambiguity). For $f(z) = (y - z)^2$,

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y - z_i)^2 - (y - \bar{z})^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (z_i - \bar{z})^2.$$

Thus $\mathfrak{C}_{n,f} = 1$. This is the classical exact ambiguity decomposition for regression ensembles.

Example 5 (Log-loss ensemble gain). Suppose an ensemble member assigns probability $p_i \in (0, 1]$ to the correct class and the averaged ensemble assigns probability

$$\bar{p} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n p_i.$$

For the log loss $f(p) = -\log p$, Jensen's inequality gives

$$-\log \bar{p} \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n -\log p_i.$$

The improvement of the averaged probabilistic predictor over the average individual log loss is

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n -\log p_i + \log \bar{p}.$$

Since $f''(p) = p^{-2}$ is nonincreasing, the reflected atom-mass theorem gives

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n -\log p_i + \log \bar{p} \geq \mathfrak{C}_n^{\log}(\bar{p}) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - \bar{p})^2,$$

with the sharp equal-weight constant obtained from the logarithmic example. Thus prediction diversity, measured by variance of the probabilities assigned to the correct class, forces a quantitative log-loss ensemble gain.

This interpretation connects the present finite-atom Jensen bounds with the ambiguity and diversity viewpoint in ensemble learning. The result is not an algorithmic statement; it is a sharp deterministic inequality for the Jensen gap under equal ensemble weights.

12 Two-sided condition number

When both sharp constants are finite, the ratio

$$\kappa_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = \frac{D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu)}{C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu)}$$

measures how tightly the variance determines the Jensen gap on \mathcal{A}_α at mean μ . The sharp inequalities give

$$C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) \text{Var}(X) \leq J_f(X) \leq D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) \text{Var}(X),$$

so $\kappa_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = 1$ means that the Jensen gap is exactly a multiple of the variance on the whole admissible class.

Proposition 2 (Basic condition-number facts). *Let $f \in C^2([0, 1])$ be convex with nondecreasing f'' .*

(i) *If f is quadratic with positive quadratic coefficient, then*

$$C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = \frac{1}{2}f'', \quad \kappa_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = 1.$$

(ii) *If $f(t) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $t \uparrow 1$ and $\mu \geq \alpha$, then*

$$D_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = +\infty, \quad \kappa_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) = +\infty.$$

(iii) *For $f(t) = t^3$, $\alpha = 1/3$, and $\mu = 1/2$,*

$$\frac{5}{4} \operatorname{Var}(X) \leq \mathbb{E}X^3 - \frac{1}{8} \leq \frac{7}{4} \operatorname{Var}(X), \quad \kappa_{\alpha,+}^{t^3} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) = \frac{7}{5}.$$

Proof. For a quadratic function, the Jensen gap is exactly $(f''/2) \operatorname{Var}(X)$, so the lower and upper sharp constants coincide.

The second statement is the infinite-barrier proposition above.

For $f(t) = t^3$, the lower constant was computed in the monomial example. With $\alpha = 1/3$ and $\mu = 1/2$, it gives $C = 5/4$. For the upper constant, the two-point upper family gives

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}X^3 - \mu^3}{\operatorname{Var}(X)} = 3\mu + \mu u \frac{1 - 2\alpha}{1 - \alpha}.$$

This is nondecreasing in u , and at

$$u = V_{\alpha,\mu} = \min \{1, 2\} = 1$$

it gives

$$D = 3 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1 - 2/3}{2/3} = \frac{7}{4}.$$

The ratio is therefore $(7/4)/(5/4) = 7/5$. □

13 Comparison with unrestricted bounds

This section explains precisely how the present bounds differ from the classical unrestricted Jensen–variance bounds, in particular those of Liao–Berg [2]. For a differentiable convex function f and fixed mean μ , set

$$q_\mu(t) = \frac{f(t) - f(\mu) - f'(\mu)(t - \mu)}{(t - \mu)^2}, \quad t \neq \mu, \quad q_\mu(\mu) = \frac{1}{2}f''(\mu).$$

Then

$$J_f(X) = \mathbb{E} [q_\mu(X)(X - \mu)^2].$$

Therefore the unrestricted interval bound is

$$\inf_{t \in I} q_\mu(t) \operatorname{Var}(X) \leq J_f(X) \leq \sup_{t \in I} q_\mu(t) \operatorname{Var}(X).$$

This is the Liao–Berg mechanism. In endpoint-monotone cases, this unrestricted mechanism is approached by distributions that put a vanishing amount of mass near the endpoint at which q_μ is smallest.

The present theorem solves a different extremal problem. We restrict to finite atomic laws satisfying

$$\mathbb{P}(X = t) \geq \alpha \quad (t \in \text{supp } X).$$

Thus the endpoint mechanism with a vanishing atom is not admissible. For functions with nondecreasing curvature, the sharp lower constant is instead obtained by a two-point law with lower atom mass exactly α . Consequently, whenever q_μ is minimized at the lower endpoint,

$$C_{\alpha,+}^f(\mu) \geq q_\mu(0),$$

and the inequality is typically strict for nonquadratic functions. As $\alpha \downarrow 0$, the atom-mass constraint disappears and the constants return to the unrestricted endpoint constant.

Example 6 (Nesbitt-type function). *Let*

$$f(t) = \frac{t}{1-t}, \quad \mu = \alpha = \frac{1}{3}.$$

The unrestricted Liao–Berg lower constant is

$$q_{1/3}(0) = \frac{0 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{9}{4}(0 - \frac{1}{3})}{(0 - \frac{1}{3})^2} = \frac{9}{4}.$$

The atom-mass theorem gives

$$C_{1/3,+}^f(1/3) = 3.$$

Hence for equal weights $t_1 + t_2 + t_3 = 1$,

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{t_i}{1-t_i} \geq \frac{3}{2} + 3 \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(t_i - \frac{1}{3}\right)^2,$$

whereas the unrestricted interval mechanism gives only the coefficient $9/4$.

Example 7 (Cubic function). *Let*

$$f(t) = t^3, \quad \mu = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \alpha = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Then

$$q_{1/2}(0) = \frac{0 - \frac{1}{8} - \frac{3}{4}(0 - \frac{1}{2})}{(0 - \frac{1}{2})^2} = 1.$$

The atom-mass theorem gives the sharper constant

$$C_{1/3,+}^{t^3} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{5}{4}.$$

Thus

$$\mathbb{E}X^3 - \frac{1}{8} \geq \frac{5}{4} \text{Var}(X)$$

for all admissible atomic laws, while the unrestricted interval estimate gives only $\text{Var}(X)$.

Example 8 (Quadratic degeneracy). *If $f(t) = t^2$, then*

$$J_f(X) = \text{Var}(X).$$

In this case the Liao–Berg constant and the atom-mass constant coincide. The present phenomenon is therefore genuinely nonquadratic: for a quadratic function the Jensen gap is already exactly the variance.

The same distinction applies to Pittenger’s sharp mean–variance bounds. Pittenger constructs a two-point law with prescribed mean and variance and one point at a distinguished endpoint; this is the classical two-point extremal principle behind many Jensen mean–variance bounds. The present paper does not claim novelty for the two-point principle itself. Rather, it solves the atom-mass constrained quotient problem: after normalizing the Jensen gap by the variance, we optimize over finite atomic laws satisfying $\mathbb{P}(X = t) \geq \alpha$. Under the monotone-curvature assumptions, this extra optimization forces the endpoint atom to have exactly the minimal admissible mass α . In this sense the results below may be viewed as sharp atom-mass optimizations of Pittenger-type extremality, together with explicit finite-sum applications.

14 Remarks and further directions

The monotone-curvature assumption is a transparent way to state the coordinatewise monotonicity of second divided differences used in the collapse arguments. A fixed-mean Bregman quotient q_μ explains the variance-weighted form of the Jensen quotient, but fixed-mean monotonicity alone is not enough for the tail collapses. Outside this monotonicity class, the two-point collapse principle should not be expected without additional hypotheses.

Another direction is to impose additional restrictions, such as two-sided atom-mass bounds or separation of support points. In that setting, the extremal problem becomes a finite active-set or packing problem rather than a two-point problem.

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